

Deliverable D4

Title

Calibration procedure for testing machines to extend the traceability chain from static to continuous forces which can be used for forces in the range of 1 N to 1 MN.

EMPIR Grant Agreement number

18SIB08

Project short name

ComTraForce

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Leading partner

Andy Knott (NPL)

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